

Electron Spin Resonance of some Nitroxide Free Radicals. Nitroxide from Homopiperazine and Dodecamethyleneimine

HAMZA A. HUSSAIN* and WALEED A. A. KUDER

Chemistry Department, College of Science, University of Baghdad, Jadiriya, Baghdad, Iraq

Manuscript received 2 February 1987, accepted 1 June 1988

Nitroxide free radicals from homopiperazine and dodecamethyleneimine have been prepared and their esr spectra reported.

Linewidth alternation due to conformational interconversion is observed in the homopiperazine case, while in case of the nitroxide from dodecamethyleneimine the spectrum was not well-resolved at room temperature, but nitrogen and hydrogen splittings were measurable at 70°.

It is easy to prepare and study nitroxide radicals of type I ($n=2,3,4,5,\dots$). Previously we described¹⁻³ the esr spectra of radicals with $n=2,3,4,5,6$.

I

Six-membered ring inversion produces an alternating linewidth effect⁴, thus in radicals when $n=5$ or 6, derived from heptamethyleneimine and octamethyleneimine, strong esr spectra were observed⁵. The spectra of both the radicals are strongly temperature-dependent but can be analysed in terms of the expected nitrogen triplet and β -proton quintet. Several papers appeared in the literature dealing with esr studies of several kinds of nitroxide free radicals⁶⁻⁷. Little work has been reported on radicals with medium size rings, apart from an investigation of cycloalkane semidiones containing six to twelve carbon atom^{8,9}.

We now report our observations on the nitroxides from homopiperazine and dodecamethyleneimine. In the case of homopiperazine, which has been chosen to compare it with hexamethyleneimine⁸, a complicated spectra were observed; however, an approximate analysis has been performed which accounts for the main features observed and gives estimates of the activation energies for ring inversion. In the dodecamethyleneimine, no resolution was observed at room temperature but heating the mixture to about 60° gave a better resolved spectra which could be analysed. The purpose of choosing this compound is to demonstrate the applicability of this method to prepare nitroxides and to have some information about its structure.

Experimental

The radicals were prepared by the oxidation of the amines with hydrogen peroxides as described previously¹. Homopiperazine and dodecamethyleneimine (Aldrich) were used as such. Ethanol was added to increase the solubility of the amines.

The esr spectra (Figs. 1 and 2) were recorded with a Varian E-109 spectrometer. Coupling constants were measured with an accuracy of ± 0.1 G. Variable temperature measurements were done using Varian E-257 variable temperature accessories. The values of coupling constants were for homopiperazine $a_N=15.5$ G, $a_H(\beta)=11$ G and for dodecamethyleneimine $a_N=16$ G, $a_H(\beta)=10.5$ G.

Results and Discussion

The esr spectra of homopiperazine nitroxide radical are temperature-dependent. The radicals are sufficiently stable for observation to be made upto 80°. The intensities of the quintets approach the 1 : 4 : 6 : 4 : 1 at high temperature which is expected for four equivalent proton; there is however one difference, in the spectra of piperidine and morpholine nitroxides⁸ the $M=\pm 2$ lines and four components of the $M=0$ lines were unaffected by ring inversion and gave 1 : 4 : 1 pattern of sharp peaks in the limit of extreme broadening. In the medium size rings the $M=0$ and $M=\pm 2$ lines become comparable in intensity and clearly more than two of the six hyperfine components are affected by the conformational changes. The reason for this is due to the complexity of the stereochemistry of medium sized rings compared with cyclohexane.

The calculation of Hendrikson predicts a boat-chair form as the lowest conformation of cyclooctane¹⁰⁻¹², but there are five other isomers with energies within 2 kcal of the ground state. The lowest form of cyclononane is probably a twist-boat-chair of D_8 symmetry with a lower symmetry isomer 2.2 kcal higher in energy^{10,11}. In contrast,

Fig. 1. ESR spectra of homopiperazine nitroxide at 35 and 70°.

Fig. 2. ESR spectra of dodecamethylene nitroxide at 60°.

the chair forms of cyclohexane are 5.6 kcal lower in energy than the twist-boat-isomers.

The assumption that the spectral density is linearly related to a correlation time with an Arrhenius type temperature-dependence means that the overall activation energy for ring inversion can be determined in a manner similar to that used in the six-membered rings^{2,3}. If A_1 and A_2 are the amplitudes of the $M=1$ and $M=2$ hyperfine components, a plot of $\log 2(A_2/A_1)^{1/2} - 1$ against $1/T$ should be linear with slope $E_a/2.307 R^{1/2}$ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plots of the linewidths vs $1/T$ for homopiperazine nitroxide.

In this way we have found the activation energy of 1.9 ± 0.2 kcal mol⁻¹ for homopiperazine. In the seven-membered rings conformational changes occur via pseudo-rotation. We have to mention here that in hexamethylene nitroxide the temperature variation did not change the shape of ESR spectra¹ and this is probably due to the faster interconversion in the case of the ring containing one nitrogen atom.

ESR spectra of the nitroxide from dodecamethyleneimine was not observed at room temperature, but heating the sample to 60° gave a good spectra (Fig. 2), which could be analysed in terms of the expected nitrogen triplet and β -proton quintet, also in this spectra several lines are affected by the conformational change.

References

1. A. HUDSON and H. A. HUSSAIN, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1968, 251.
2. A. HUDSON and H. A. HUSSAIN, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1968, 993.
3. A. HUDSON and H. A. HUSSAIN, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1968, 1346.
4. G. CHAPPELET-LETOURNIEUX, H. LEMAIR and A. RASSAT, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1965, 3283.

HUSSAIN & KUDER : ELECTRON SPIN RESONANCE OF SOME NITROXIDE FREE RADICALS

5. D. P. VELLOSO and A. RASSAT, *J. Chem. Res. Synop.*, 1979, **5**, 168.
6. A. ROCKENBAUER, M. GYOR, L. JOKAY and F. TUDOS, *Adv. Mol. Relax. Interact. Processes*, 1979, **15**, 311.
7. A. ROCKENBAUER, M. GYOR, L. JOKAY and F. TUDOS, *Adv. Mol. Relax. Interact. Processes*, 1980, **18**, 231.
8. J. W. LOWN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1965, **43**, 3294.
9. J. W. LOWN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 591.
10. J. B. HENDRICKSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **80**, 4854.
11. J. B. HENDRICKSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 7036.
12. J. B. HENDRICKSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 7047.
13. N. M. ATHERTON and A. E. GOGGINS, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 1399.